

A Second Soul: Celebrating the Many Languages of
Programming

Festschrift in Honor of Peter Thiemann's Sixtieth Birthday

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August 2024

Research group in 2000 (est.)

Research group in 2009

Research group in 2010

Research group in 2011

Research group in 2015

Preface

It is with great pleasure that we present this Festschrift in honor of Professor Peter Thiemann on the occasion of his sixtieth birthday. This volume celebrates Peter’s many contributions to the field of programming languages. The topics Peter worked on since his first publication in 1990 (according to DBLP) are diverse and best summarized by a picture:

We generated the picture above by assigning up to three topics to a carefully reviewed list of the 207 entries in DBLP for Peter. Notably, we chose to omit the topic “functional programming” from the list, as a significant number of Peter’s publications could be classified under this category.

Peter is not only an outstanding researcher but also an excellent teacher and advisor. The three editors of this Festschrift were part of the Proglang research group at the University of Freiburg between 2005 and 2011. Our doctoral period coincided with a rather exciting phase for the research group. The local organization of ICFP and IFL 2007 was a very challenging but also a rewarding project. During the various tasks — conference website, catering, Wifi setup, last-minute transportation of a huge screen across the city with a camping bus, missing beds in the Freiburg youth hostel — we learned to rely on each other and tackle challenges together. Peter was always there and provided the necessary overview (and sometimes the early morning coffee at registration).

It was also during this time that the band of our research group was formed. We were lucky to have an (almost) perfect line-up with drums, electric guitar, bass, electric piano/organ and triangle. We met once a month at Peter’s house in the basement and gradually developed a small repertoire. And Uta made sure that we didn’t have to go home hungry afterwards.

Thanks to Peter’s international connections, some of his students had the remarkable opportunity to participate in research groups in Canada, Denmark, and Argentina. These experiences were not only invaluable but also significantly advanced our PhD theses during this period.

Publication successes (and failures), trips with canoes and scooters, retreats at the Schauinslandhütte, conference trips to the other side of the world, writing research proposals, but also the conception and implementation of teaching formats such as “supervised programming” — a PhD with Peter means a fundamental and comprehensive guide to academic work and life. His enthusiasm for research and teaching is contagious. So it’s no coincidence that so many of his doctoral students followed his path and qualified for positions at universities.

And yet these anecdotes document only a small part of Peter’s work. In this Festschrift, his friends and colleagues have collected contributions on common research topics and experiences. We hope you enjoy reading it as much as we enjoy putting it together!

Happy birthday, Peter!

August 2024

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A Tribute to Peter Thiemann

John Hughes

It comes as a little bit of a shock to me that a youngster like Peter is turning 60! I've known him for a very long time, so I thought I would remind him of some of the ways our paths have interconnected over the years.

I think I first met Peter at a meeting that Neil Jones organised; at any rate, I remember Peter giving a very nice talk, and Neil turning to me and remarking how smart that young man seemed to be. I could only agree!

Peter and I were both very inspired by the breakthrough in partial evaluation made in Neil's group in Copenhagen in the mid 1980s (Jones, Sestoft, & Søndergaard, 1989). Peter was very active in the area, turning out articles left, right and centre, and then in 1995 he co-organised a Dagstuhl seminar on the topic (Danvy, Glück, & Thiemann, 1996), to which I was invited.

Since I was attending a seminar on partial evaluation, I needed to do something relevant to speak about... and I had an idea for specializing types, which would enable me to perform Jones-optimal specialization of a typed programming language, essentially by specializing away the universal type needed in a typed self-interpreter. This was one of the 'challenging problems' that Neil Jones identified in the 1980s, which had been open for about a decade (Jones N. D., 1988). My type specializer used enriched type-inference rules instead of an enriched self-interpreter; I built a prototype and gave a talk about it, Peter was very excited, and we had a great discussion at the seminar. The proceedings were put together after-the-fact, which gave me time to write a paper on the results—one of the papers I am still most proud of (Hughes, 1996).

My paper addressed the simply typed lambda calculus. What about richer programming languages? What about imperative programming languages? These were questions that Peter wanted to address. So (in collaboration with Dirk Dussart) we developed a version of the type specialiser that could handle state, based on Moggi's computational lambda-calculus, and indeed, we were able to specialise a self-interpreter for the stateful computational lambda-calculus Jones-optimally (Dussart, Hughes, & Thiemann, 1997). Peter went on to build a simpler typed Jones-optimal specialiser, by distilling just the essential ideas out of my type specialiser (Thiemann, 2000), and to use the technique to inject security checks into mobile code (Thiemann, 2001).

This work extended the semantics of the language to be specialised. The other obvious direction was to extend the types; my original work was for the simply typed lambda-calculus... so what about polymorphic types? This question was addressed by Pablo Martinez Lopez, for his PhD at the University of Buenos Aires under my remote supervision (Lopez, 2005). And who better to examine such a thesis than... Peter? This led to a very enjoyable visit to Argentina for both of us; I hope these photographs will help bring back some happy memories.

Pablo and Peter getting ready to order some food; Peter at a souvenir shop

Peter and Pablo outside the magnificent cathedral in La Plata; Peter admiring the interior

The second story I want to tell starts rather similarly: I had accepted an invitation to give a keynote at *Mathematics of Program Construction* in 1998, so I thought I needed to do something relevant to speak about. At the time I was very interested in monads, but frustrated that Swierstra and Duponcheel’s parsing library could not be given a monadic interface (Swierstra & Duponcheel, 1996), because it gathered both static and dynamic information about each parser. But I could see how to fit it into a more general categorical framework, so I designed an abstraction I called ‘arrows’ and talked about it at MPC. As a keynote speaker, I had not submitted (or written!) a paper, but nevertheless I was invited to contribute to a ‘selected papers’ special issue, so I had to write a paper quickly (Hughes, 2000).

So far I had used arrows to build parsers, but I wanted more than one example for the paper. There was another problem that had been bothering me greatly, namely writing CGI scripts. These were used at the time to build dynamic web pages, but all of the code ran on the web server, and asking the user a question meant generating an HTML form on one page, whose contents would be interpreted in the next HTTP request made by the client, often handled by an entirely different CGI script. Call-back hell, in other words—a software engineering nightmare. I thought I could see a way to finesse call-back hell by defining an arrow type for *resumable* computations, that would maintain a path from the root of the computation to the current execution point, and save that path on the client when generating a form, so that the *same* CGI script could use the path to resume at the same point, and receive the form contents. I realised this could also be done with a monad, but I thought an arrow would be far more efficient.

As I was working on this, I went to a working group meeting in Recife, Brazil, where I spoke about my work in progress, to an audience including Peter. Peter was also interested in dynamic web pages, but he realized that there was no need for an arrow in this case, and the monadic solution would work perfectly well in practice! He built his WASH/CGI library using that idea (Thiemann, 2002). Since Peter’s implementation was so much more complete and full-featured than mine then I just adopted it for my web programming needs. In particular, I built a web system in Haskell for handling lab submissions in my functional programming course, with automated assignment to teaching assistants, handling of resubmissions, invocation of plagiarism detection tools, etc etc. I used it—and I used WASH/CGI whenever I needed a dynamic web system—for years and years.

I mentioned the working group meeting in 1999 at which I showed my CGI arrow ideas to Peter. This was a meeting of IFIP working group 2.8, on Functional Programming—a regular informal by-invitation workshop on topics related at least loosely to functional programming, which has been meeting at least once a year since 1988. These meetings are probably where Peter and I run into each other most often. I am a founding member of the group, and Peter joined very early on (and is now the Chair). These meetings are great for collaboration, providing plenty of time for discussion and even doing some work together. To foster that atmosphere, some at least of the meetings are in quite secluded spots. Peter will remember these in particular:

Frauenchiemsee, an abbey on its own island in a lake near Munich

West Point, where passing students saluted us, and called us “Sir!”

Here are pictures of Peter at a few of these events:

Peter at group meetings in Estonia (2005), West Point (2004), and Edinburgh (2017)

It’s been great to see Peter so regularly over the years at these events.

Peter has been a valued colleague and friend over the years, and if I should remark on two things that I value most, I would say it’s his infectious enthusiasm and the unflinching elegance of his work. It’s an honour to be able to help celebrate his excellent career. Happy birthday, Peter!

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Programming with Context-free Session Types

On the occasion of the symposium in honor of Peter Thiemann's 60th birthday

Vasco T. Vasconcelos

July 31, 2024

Picture a computation where concurrent processes communicate by exchanging messages on bidirectional channels. In such a setting processes may write the result of computations on channels, and they may as well read values provided by other processes. Now picture a channel shared by two processes only. Because channels are bidirectional, the two processes must agree on who writes first on the channel. Once that agreed, it naturally follows that the other process must read first. Communication may proceed after the first interaction: on the second communication the read/write role of the processes may be maintained or possibly reversed.

Code for the two processes at stake is usually written independently. Then, a common interface must be pre-established. This is common to many other realms of software development: unambiguous interfaces between communicating partners assure that software composition does not go wrong. That is the case, for example, of a function signature in a programming language with procedural abstraction [8].

In the domain of interest—message passing concurrency—the interfaces between processes are channels and the patterns of message exchanges on a single channel form what we call the *protocol* of the channel. The language of session types is particularly suited to describe such interfaces, that is, to describe communication protocols.

Session types were introduced by Honda in 1993 [6]. A sentence from the abstract reads “types denote freely composable structures of dyadic interaction”. The elements of interaction include writing on a channel and reading from a channel. Such elements may be composed by the sequential composition operator on types.

In the subsequent five years, two further papers by Honda and colleagues shaped what is now known as the field of session types [7, 10]. These works put forward the idea of using session types to describe message exchanges on communication channels from within programming languages.

Realistic protocols may repeat themselves after a while: think of a server deciding the primality of integer values, one after the other. Such a protocol may be described by a regular language: the Kleene star of the sequence composed of a read (of an integer) and a write (of a boolean value).

All subsequent developments on session types are based on regular languages. And there is a strong reason for that: deciding type equivalence is a well-known polynomial endeavour. All subsequent works, NO! In 2014 Peter came up with the idea that session types could be more than mere regular languages. In order to stream tree-like structures (such as JSON or XML) on channels, he proposed context-free session types. Looking back, from a 2024 standpoint, this was a “back to the classics”, back to the 1993 work by Honda [6], back to composing elements of interaction (read and write) by means of sequential composition.

Peter presented his idea to the author of this memoir in the “NII Shonan Meeting on Software Contracts for Communication, Monitoring, and Security” in Japan, May 2014. Interaction progressed by email. Peter soon realised that there was a rich theory of type equivalence lurking behind the inoffensive-looking sequential composition type operator (the semicolon operator on types). For example: sequential

composition must be associative. Later, a neutral element was introduced for the sequential composition (semicolon) operator, so that types become equipped with a monoidal structure. Peter also realised that semicolon must right-distribute over choice.

It turned out that, in 2014, Peter and Vasco were part of the same EU COST Action: IC1201 BETTY, “Behavioural Types for Reliable Large-Scale Software Systems”. In the last day of a call for Short-term Scientific Missions, in December 2014, they started and concluded an application for the latter to visit Freiburg in February 2015. The application concluded “We propose to study a *small* change in the language of session types that makes context-free behaviours expressible and explore some of the consequences of this language extension” (the emphasis is by the author of this note).

There were further hurdles ahead: when should one deem two types equivalent? And how can one decide whether two types are equivalent? For the former question it was agreed that a good old bisimulation built on an appropriate labelled transition system would provide for an intuitive notion of type equivalence. For the second, it was pointed to the authors the close relationship between context-free session types and Basic Process Algebra [3] whose bisimilarity is known to be decidable [4].

All pieces felt finally in place. A paper, “Context-free session types”, was written and later delivered at the International Conference on Functional Programming, in 2016, Nara, Japan [11].

Such an exciting notion of types for concurrency called for a programming language to experiment with hitherto out of reach communication protocols. But alas, even when the equivalence of context-free session types had been proved decidable, no feasible algorithm would come out of the proof.

The promise of a programming language with context-free session types was hostage of a procedure to decide type equivalence, of an effective procedure that could be included in a compiler. Based on works about deciding bisimilarity of context-free processes, an algorithm was produced, implemented and tested. The first version of the FREEST programming language was released [5] in 2017, and a paper describing the type equivalence algorithm was presented at TACAS [2] in 2020. This paved the way for a journal version of the ICFP original paper [1].

From an initial implementation, mostly based on a Damas-Milner type system and first-order messages (that is, messages capable of sending values of base types only), FREEST steadily grew to incorporate impredicative polymorphism, (System F), higher-order messages (that is, messages that may transport channel ends), pattern matching on function definitions (both for data types and for external choices on session types), a notion of shared channels (channels that may be shared by an unbounded number of processes), kind inference (so that programmers need not explicitly write the kind of polymorphic term variables). At the time of this writing, the most recent addition was a notion of subtyping for context-free session types [9].

Peter is a programming languages guy: he loves programming; programming in stimulating languages, including Agda and FREEST. There are many sorts of applications that fit naturally in languages with context-free session types. A paramount example is the problem of streaming tree-like data (JSON or XML objects, or simply trees of values of some sort), as opposed to streaming list-like data that falls naturally under the reach of regular session types.

We conclude this short notice by presenting a program to send a tree, node by node, on a channel and another for retrieving one such tree from a channel and rebuild the original tree, that is essentially the example in the ICFP paper, only that written in modern guise.

We start with the declaration of a (polymorphic) datatype for trees. This could be Haskell or FREEST.

```
data Tree a = Leaf | Node (Tree a) a (Tree a)
```

We then declare the corresponding channel type, as seen from the side of the writer. Writers select either the `LeafC` or the `NodeC` option. In the former case nothing else is sent on the channel (denoted by

`Skip`); in the later case writers must send a tree, followed by a value of type `a`, followed by another tree.

```
type TreeC a = +{LeafC: Skip, NodeC: TreeC ; !a ; TreeC}
```

All channels in FREEST must be closed: at one endpoint one closes a channel (of type `Close`); at the other end one waits for the channel (of type `Wait`) to be closed. Programming in FREEST amounts to *consuming channel end points*. We start with a function that consumes an end point of an type `TreeC a ; Close` (a writer for trees). But first a handy abstraction suggested by Peter:

```
(|>) : a -> (a -> b) -> b
x |> f = f x
```

is the function application operator, left associative and in reverse order. Then, idiom

```
writer |> write tree |> close
```

can be read “with `writer` do: `write tree` and then close the channel”. `write` itself is a recursive function that pattern matches on the type constructor of the tree and either selects the `LeafC` or the `NodeC` option or the `writer` channel. In the code below we assume that the semicolon type operator binds tighter than the arrow.

```
writeTree : Tree a -> TreeC a ; Close -> ()
writeTree tree writer = writer |> write tree |> close
  where
    write : Tree -> TreeC ; a -> a
    write Leaf c =
      c |> select LeafC
    write (Node l x r) c =
      c |> select NodeC |> write l |> send x |> write r
```

We may now work out a function to consume the reader end of the channel, a channel whose type may be abbreviated as `Dual (TreeC a) ; Wait`. We start by reading a tree from the channel end, then wait for the channel to be closed, and finally return the tree just read. Reading from a channel returns a pair composed of the element read and the channel end point where to continue the interaction.

```
readTree : Dual (TreeC a) ; Wait -> Tree a
readTree reader =
  let (tree, reader) = read reader in wait reader ; tree
  where
    read : Dual TreeC ; a -> (Tree, a)
    read (LeafC c) = (Leaf, c)
    read (NodeC c) =
      let (l, c) = read c in
      let (x, c) = receive c in
      let (r, c) = read c in (Node l x r, c)
```

The exploration of the potentialities of context-free session types has just begun. It has been a pleasure, and a constant challenge, working with Peter in the last few years; we sincerely hope it will remain so for many good years.

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Teaching Functional Programming (Experience Report)

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This paper reports on a decades-long journey to develop approaches and material for teaching functional programming to beginning students as well as experienced software developers.

1 Introduction

In 1997, the computer-science faculty of the University of Tübingen commissioned Peter Thiemann and me to teach the introductory course. While the course itself eventually fell victim to institutional quibbles, Peter and I started thinking about teaching the introductory course that year. Subsequently, I actually started teaching the introductory class in Tübingen in 1999, off and on until 2010, and Peter ended up teaching an introductory course in Freiburg. We collaborated on evaluating and improving our respective courses. My work continued after I moved to industry, teaching commercial trainings in functional programming for professional programmers to this day.

Teaching beginners, especially at the University level, is a hard challenge. If the class is large enough (and it usually is), some students will always pick up on the teacher's enthusiasm and give positive feedback while the other students struggle and, in many cases, give up.

Thus, the effort summarized in this paper focusses on inclusion—enabling as many students as possible, independent of their backgrounds, to learn how to program effectively. The paper covers the following aspects:

Evolution (Section 2) motivates the need for iteratively improving the course using evaluation and feedback.

Systematic Programming (Section 3) describes the central didactic tenet of the course that emerged.

Language Design (Section 4) briefly touches on the language-design aspects of a good course.

Commercial Training and Functional Architecture (Section 5) describes how the methods from the introductory course carry over to professional programmers.

Future Work (Section 6) covers possible avenues for further improvement and expansion.

2 Evolution

A teacher, when designing a course, will usually rely on their background, their preferences, and their intuition. However, unlike the students, they are (usually) already proficient in the subject matter, and this means that their cognition now works differently from their students' [19, 20]. Therefore, what

seems compelling and easy to the teacher is often not so for the student.¹ Relying on external input from didactics experts is also not guaranteed to produce good results.²

Thus, feedback and iterative improvement are necessary to evolve a preliminary design into a working course. Our first course at the University of Tübingen was in 1999, and we realized in 2004 that we needed to improve on the original design. As the PLT project had done before us [8], we embarked onto analyzing what was going well and what was not. A book written as part of that effort [14] was, in retrospect, no more than a snapshot along the way.

Note that student evaluations that universities often conduct do not yield what specific parts and aspects are problematic. Consequently, we conducted a more detailed course evaluation jointly with Peter Thiemann’s group [4, 3], eventually replacing all of the original material [17]. The evaluation involved collecting observations from in-class exercises and a detailed analysis of exam results.

Our activities eventually led to the formation of the *DeinProgramm* project³ dedicated to developing material for teaching programming.

3 Systematic Programming

As anyone who has taught programming can attest, it is often baffling to teachers that students somehow cannot figure out the “next step” to take when solving a particular exercise, even though it is “obvious” to the teacher. This is because as teachers we rely on experience and knowledge we do not communicate explicitly. Many textbooks similarly fail to explain what steps beginners can take to solve a programming problem, instead relying on examples to implicitly communicate the methodology used to create them. Expectations that students will “teach themselves” when given the right tools [11] are similarly misplaced [2].

Matthias Felleisen’s PLT group pioneered the use of *design recipes* [9, 10], reminiscent of Jackson Structured Programming [13]. The design recipes are a collection of named, systematic techniques for deriving the building blocks (“templates”) of a function mechanically from the data it operates on. The design of the data structures, needed to apply templates, is similarly systematic. In particular, data analysis and design recipes make recursion accessible to most students, previously a subject deemed “difficult” by many teachers and students.

The design recipes’ data analysis focusses on distinguishing between sums and products. All other aspects of the design recipes flow from there. Sadly, the systematic design of data is still woefully underappreciated in the wider development community, which focusses mostly on the analysis of processes [12]. In practice, this leads to impoverished data model, foregoing the advantages of using sums and combinator models [15]. Consequently, the potential impact of systematic programming is still largely unfulfilled.

¹This is on prominent display with the well-known Wizard Book [1], the book written for the MIT introductory class. This book is compelling to many computer-science practitioners, but does not work well with beginners [9].

²As an example, when advising our introductory class, a didactics expert recommended that, instead of teaching a single systematic approach to programming (see Section 3), we should rather focus on comparing different solutions. This neglects to take into account that—without a systematic approach—many students struggle with finding a *single* solution.

³<https://www.deinprogramm.de>

4 Language Design

The design of a programming course often starts with the choice of a particular language. Unfortunately, programming languages used by developers (or researchers) generally make things difficult for learners, by several traits:

1. Most languages conflate several concepts into a single language construct or require using advanced features even in the beginning. (Algebraic data types and type classes in Haskell are notable examples.)
2. Beginners make errors, and common programming languages often give poor feedback on such mistakes [8].
3. In particular, the combination of #1 and #2 means that feedback on an error might refer to language concepts or constructs the course has not covered yet.
4. Students who have programmed previously will look up advanced programming constructs and use them inappropriately, undercutting the didactic goals of the course.

The PLT group pioneered the use of *language levels* [9] to address these problems: Students start with a small language that elides advanced features, and gives specific, tailored feedback. Later in the class, students switch to a “higher level”, extending the language with the features next covered in class.

As with other aspects of the course, the design of such language levels (and their error messages [16]) is best done iteratively. In our work on the introductory course, we started—as had the PLT group—from Scheme, and continued making changes based on feedback and classroom observations [5]. The resulting language levels ship with the Racket system [?] to this day.

The main change of our language levels over PLT’s was the introduction of *signatures*, an notation strongly reminiscent of types to describe shape of data, and the inputs and outputs of functions. This has proven tremendously helpful in aiding students’ understanding of data analysis, as well as applying the design recipes in practice.⁴ In particular, signatures are checked at run time and produce error messages with concrete examples.

While much of the language-design work has focussed on ergonomics, the language design that has emerged is quite principled in its presentation and separation of concepts, in particular the separation between sums and products, each of which has distinct, independent language constructs to support them.

5 Commercial Training and Functional Architecture

I eventually left academia, and am now CEO of Active Group, a small software consultancy. Since 2012, we had also been developing a professional training business, teaching typically 3-day classes on functional programming, in a variety of languages.

When we started teaching software developers rather than beginning students, we assumed that the didactic ideas from DeinProgramm would carry over, but that we could instead use a “professional” language directly. We assumed that the problems described in Section 4 would be familiar to professional developers, and therefore not cause problems. We discovered however that using the teaching languages developed for the intro course was slightly more effective. Essentially, the functional programming

⁴Typed languages tend to produce error messages that beginners find hard to understand, and that block making progress on an assignment, causing frustration.

course is now a highly condensed and sped-up version of the introductory course [17], and switches to a different language on the second or third day.

Until 2017, bookings for in-house courses on functional programming were sparse. Consequently, we embarked on making contact with the International Software Architecture Qualification Board (iSAQB), a German volunteer-driven association whose goal is to further education on software architecture—techniques, tools, and processes that help with managing large software projects beyond the capacity of a single person or even a single team. Together with iSAQB, we developed a curriculum on “Functional Software Architecture” as part of its Advanced-level certification [6]. The curriculum focusses on the architectural impact of immutable data, combinator models, the use of algebraic abstractions, effects, and covers functional macro architecture.

We designed a course based on the curriculum, significantly based on an architecture example developed with Peter Thiemann [18], and have been teaching it regularly since 2019. The architecture course is prefixed by a one-day introduction to functional programming based on our work on the introductory course. As with that course, we have been using feedback and experiments to evolve and improve it, making significant changes over the years. Unsurprisingly, the section on effects has undergone the most changes.

6 Future Work

The work on the introductory course is by no means finished, and interesting areas for further exploration continue to emerge, notably Jeremy Gibbons’s work on extending the design recipes by *output-based* recipes. (Most of the existing recipes are input-based.) Work also continues on the design and implementation of the teaching languages.

The design of the architecture class is still evolving, and many didactic gaps between the introductory class, which focusses on single functions, and large-scale programs remain.

A significant challenge is integrating teaching of functional programming and functional architecture with the popular disciplines of Domain-Driven Design [7] and Collaborative Modeling [12]. Both have produced viable methods for conducting and teaching some aspects of requirements analysis and software design. These are quite complementary to the techniques the functional-programming community has produced, so this has large potential benefit. However, both communities have evolved independently and, for some aspects, in different directions. (Particularly on the role of abstraction in software design.)

7 Conclusion

As much as the functional-community likes to think that functional concepts are natural and easy to understand, teaching them in a way that is accessible to a wide variety of students is difficult. To do it well requires learning from our mistakes—preferably not just our own, but also each others’.

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Memories of my PhD Years with Peter Thiemann

Simon Helsen

When I arrived in Tübingen in the fall of 1997, I was a naïve 22 year old who had little understanding of what he was getting into. Although the "Institut für Softwaretechnik" was led by Prof. Dr. Klaeren, it was Peter Thiemann, then a private lecturer, who took me under his wing. Peter had managed to secure a multi-year grant from the German Research Foundation (DFG) to work on a typed partial evaluator for ML. Upon my arrival, Peter immediately had me read various books and articles on topics like program specialization, programming language design, compiler construction, and type theory. Undoubtedly, I was ill-prepared when I came to the department, but Peter trusted that I would catch up one way or the other. With the help of Michael Sperber, who worked closely with Peter during those early years, I did slowly gain the necessary confidence.

In my first year, my German was not particularly good. I specifically recall that, as I went through the algorithm for "strongly connected components" in the German version of Reinhard Wilhelm's *Compiler Design* book, Peter suggested that I read the details in the English translation. Surprisingly, that version didn't seem to include the relevant chapter. Proactively as he was, Peter contacted Prof. Wilhelm to find out what was going on and learned that the English translation had removed some theoretical chapters deemed less "suitable" for the American market.

Around the summer of 1998, Peter received a professorship at the University of Nottingham in the functional programming languages group of Graham Hutton. Although I stayed in Tübingen and Peter regularly traveled back and forth since his family still lived in the Tübingen area, I visited Nottingham for a few days later that year. But since my stay included a weekend when Peter was not in town, and to get some useful work done, Peter had given me the keys to his office. Now, keep in mind that laptops in those days were not that widespread or powerful, and Internet access outside of universities was not ubiquitous either. Unfortunately, an overzealous and slightly obnoxious IT administrator found me in Peter's office and was extremely upset about this. You see, at English universities, there were often many restrictions for students, even graduate and PhD students, and me sitting at a professor's desk in his office was simply unthinkable. The following week, Peter got into quite a bit of trouble with the department over this violation. Fortunately, it wasn't long before Peter received a professorship at the University of Freiburg. At that point, Professor Klaeren transferred the DFG project to Peter, which also meant I was to follow Peter to Freiburg.

In the following years, Peter's department in Freiburg grew with many excellent colleagues. During this time, Peter remained an incredible mentor, often pushing interdisciplinary research. I vividly remember how he used Haskell type classes and extensions to create a domain-specific language for HTML and a more general XML schema validation. Another fun project was his Haskell-based DSL for developing web pages with full state restoration features (based on CGI - Common Gateway Interface), which I later used to implement a small World Cup betting game for my "Wohngemeinschaft". Crossing these boundaries and finding new ways to use strongly typed functional languages in various domains was something I admired of Peter. Nothing was too outrageous to try out. Similarly, when Peter wanted to learn a new area or subject, he sought out ways to make a course out of it. After all, the best way to learn something is to teach it.

All of this made me very proud to be his first PhD graduate in the fall of 2002. It cannot be over-

stated how much my thinking matured during my time with Peter. A particular skill that Peter relentlessly instilled in me was how to write a scientific paper properly. It wasn't just about writing style or bibliography but also about how to build up a paper, make sure that you define everything first before arguing with it or before delving into a proof. This skill is still of great importance in my current job when drafting technical design documents for the software products I develop.

When I moved to Canada in November 2002, Peter remained incredibly supportive and created a small grant for me to complete some journal publications while I was trying to figure out what I would do next in my career. When I married my Canadian wife in Southwestern Ontario in the fall of 2006, Peter decided to come to our wedding with Uta and his four children! Needless to say, I was very honored by this, and it shows how incredibly caring Peter is towards his students. And I must say, over the years, as I see what has happened in Peter's department, I am really happy to see how many of his students have built successful careers since leaving the department, whether in academia or industry. This is a testament to Peter's passion for excellence and academic accomplishments.

Either way, for my part, I want to thank Peter for everything! On many more years!

Simon was part of Peter's working group from September 1997 until November 2002. In November 2002, he defended his PhD thesis entitled "Region-based Program Specialization, an operational approach to offline-based partial evaluation for ML-like languages".

The Era “From PGGs to Type-Safe Web Programming”

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This paper presents two topics from Peter Thiemann’s research work which both influenced the author’s own research career and also, in the author’s opinion, are well worth a closer look: the systematic creation of efficient program generator generators and the type-safe programming of web applications.

1 Introduction

I began my university education in the mid-1990s pursuing a diploma program in computer science at the Eberhard-Karls-University in Tübingen, Germany. The department of computer science in Tübingen was small, and studying computer science was still somewhat exotic at the time, at least in Tübingen. The department was still new, in contrast to all other departments of all other faculties, most of which could look back on a centuries-old tradition of a university characterized by the humanities. The Wilhelm-Schickard-Institut, where the computer science departments were located, was based in an old military hospital on the outskirts of Tübingen.

The first year of computer science studies was rather sobering, the basic computer science course consisted of a “C++ programming course” introducing the latest OOP methods and following the definitive C++ language guide of 669 pages by the inventor of C++, Bjarne Stroustrup [4].

The compulsory lectures in mathematics, which were offered jointly to students of computer science and mathematics, were far more interesting and challenging. The first year as a computer science student was anything but what I had imagined computer science studies would be like and rather disillusioning.

The lecture “Fundamentals of Programming Languages”, offered by the chair of programming languages and read by lecturer Peter, appeared in the course offerings of the third semester. In the spirit of a diploma student at the time, naturally following the university motto “Attempto!” (“I dare!”), there was no question that I had to attend this lecture, which seemed to be somewhat “outside the mainstream”.

The lecture was not a classical tour through the world of programming languages at that time like similar lectures of this title, but followed the “Hitch-Hiker’s Guide to the Meta-Universe” [2] (see Footnote 6 in [1]) as a textbook. After studying the Scheme programming language, we wrote small interpreters internalizing the the basic concepts of programming languages, such as different variable-binding concepts (“static” vs “dynamic”), function abstraction, state, references, inheritance or the continuation-passing style (CPS).

The lecture was a revelation in several directions: it showed that there are other trends in in university computer science besides C++ and OOP, that often the best way to penetrate a problem is to “do it yourself” and implement it, and that the research area “programming languages” is a very interesting mixture of “theoretical computer science”, of course based on the lambda calculus, and “practical computer science”, shaping the basis of every programmer’s daily work.

2 Partial Evaluation and Efficient Compiler Generation

The lecture and a subsequent student research project on the nature of the continuation passing style, following a seminal paper by Hatcliff and Danvy [3] and also supervised by Peter Thiemann, gave me a first insight into the tools of programming language research and the techniques of Peter Thiemann’s research focus at the time: partial evaluation, and the techniques involved in partial evaluation such as binding time analyses, code specialization, program generators and compiler generators (a.k.a. “cogens”).

Partial evaluation is the transformation of computer programs so that for a program for which some of its inputs are already known at an earlier time (the so-called “static inputs”) is “specialized” into another program in which the statically known program parts are already preevaluated, and a so-called residual program is generated, which has only the remaining inputs as input (the so-called “dynamic inputs”) and is able to perform the remaining calculation to arrive at the same result.

In “online partial evaluation”, a decision is made during the specialization step as to which program parts are pre-evaluated and which are redisualized. In “offline partial evaluation”, this decision takes place in an upstream, independent analysis step, the so-called “binding time analysis” (BTA), before a separate specialization step.

A program generator generator (PGG) or compiler generator is a system that performs such a “partial evaluation” in several stages. When a program p and a specification defining which input parameters are statically known are entered, it generates a so-called program generator which, after entering the statically known input values, generates a specialized residual program for p , which only requires and evaluates the remaining “dynamic” input in order to then arrive at the same result.

It has long been known in “partial evaluation” that a PGG can be generated by “double self-application” of a generic “partial evaluator”. However, the resulting PGG resulting from such a double self-application is unnecessarily inefficient, as unnecessary tagging information and evaluation steps of the original evaluator remain in the PGG (the so-called “interpretative overhead”).

The PGGs generated by self-application were therefore later supplemented by work that showed how PGGs or cogens can be defined “manually” so that these inefficiencies can be avoided. However, it remained unclear at first how such a system could be generated systematically and correctly.

Peter Thiemann’s work was the first to show how an efficient “cogen” can be systematically derived from a two-level interpreter in the form of a so-called combinator library, by systematically applying well-known techniques such as higher-order abstract syntax, deforestation and untagging to the original interpreter, first for dynamically typed programming languages such as Scheme [5], and later for statically typed languages [6]. The techniques are universally applicable and transferable to other programming languages or domain-specific languages, and can therefore serve as a starting point for different compiler generators.

3 Web Programming in a Type-Safe Setting

Peter Thiemann also successfully applied the approach of creating a type-safe combinator library later, in the early 2000s, — in the meantime head of the “Programming Languages department” at the institute of computer science at the University of Freiburg — in another domain, the creation of web applications, i.e. applications that are made available to users via the World Wide Web and operated via web browsers.

The WASH Haskell library and the associated publications show how web applications can be developed with fundamental advantages in contrast to the then prevailing approaches to web development in other programming languages. In particular, Peter Thiemann’s research demonstrates how to make use

of Haskell’s static type system,

- to embed HTML pages and fragments within Haskell source code, ensuring that only *well-formed* HTML can be embedded [7],
- to write entire server-side web applications as single programs, where session state is transparently managed across all steps of a session,
- to enhance HTML in such web applications by input elements that are extended by type-safe callback functions which naturally express the continuation in the session history, and
- to incorporate persistent state into web sessions in a controlled way, either on the client-side or on the server-side [8].

4 Conclusion

These two works show only a small part of Peter Thiemann’s scientific work, but I remember them both very much as great works that originally brought innovations and simplifications, each in their own domain.

A question that naturally arises: where is the “cogen” for type-safe web sessions with callbacks [9]?

Matthias was part of Peter’s working group from January 2001 until February 2007. In April 2007, he defended his PhD thesis entitled “Multi-Tier Programming”.

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Mastering the Academic Triathlon

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Triathlon is usually a sport that involves swimming, cycling, and running. Peter is known to be a triathlete, and in addition to the classical triathlon, Peter also masters another triathlon: the one as a research group leader at a university consisting of teaching, academic research, and employee development. The analogy of both highlights the parallels in diversity of skills, endurance, and adaptability. Both require commitment, strategic planning, and the ability to multi-task effectively, and success is a testament to an individual's resilience, dedication, and diverse skill set – something also reflected in Peter's professional career.

Like most of Peter's PhD students, I first got to know Peter as a professor and lecturer during my studies at the University of Freiburg. Through seminars and lectures, Peter introduced me to the exciting world of programming languages and program analysis and aroused my interest in this subject. My fascination for this research field ultimately led me to write my master's thesis at the Chair of Programming Languages and subsequently accept a position as a PhD student at Peter's research group. As supervisor and mentor, Peter introduced me to the world of academic research and university teaching.

During this time, I got to know Peter as a highly motivated researcher – a tinkerer, always with his hands on the theorems. In countless sessions, we discussed academic problems, took theorems apart, or buried ourselves deeper and deeper in mathematical complexity. I remember our work on regular expressions, where we challenged each other almost every morning with counterexamples and theory, too fondly. And I'll always remember all the hours and night shifts we spent together writing and polishing our academic publications to their best.

In addition to research, I shared Peter's passion for sport. His unwavering enthusiasm and perseverance have always been a source of inspiration for me. I have been consistently motivated by the tenacity, will, and perseverance with which Peter pursues his goals. My collaboration with Peter has significantly influenced many of my characteristics.

Thank you, Peter, for your mentoring, knowledge, and, most importantly, for entrusting me with the opportunity to write my doctoral thesis at your research group. Under your guidance, I have not only learned a great deal but also experienced significant personal and professional growth. I am deeply grateful for your influence and support, which have been instrumental in this journey.

Peter, I wish you all the best for your future professional and athletic projects.

Dowsing: Search by types, fast, correct and complete

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One essential task of programmers is to use the right library and function. But what is the right function? Most developers use their experience and knowledge of the ecosystem to intuit where to look for. Tools like Sherloc or Hoople provide textual search in an ecosystem of functions, easing the quest of the developer.

We present Dowsing, a tool to search OCaml functions by their types: the developer provides a type, and Dowsing finds a function whose type is suitable. More precisely, it finds any functions whose type is more general, up to a set of isomorphisms such as currying or reordering of arguments. Unlike other similar tools, results are guaranteed to be sound (the type does match) and complete (all such functions are found).

Dowsing uses several techniques based on term indexing, unification and constraint solving to scale to medium-sized ecosystems, which we will present during this talk.

Summa Summarum: Moessner’s Theorem without Dynamic Programming

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Seventy years on, Moessner’s theorem and Moessner’s process – i.e., the additive computation of integral powers – continue to fascinate. They have given rise to a variety of elegant proofs, to an implementation in hardware, to generalizations, and now even to a popular video, “The Moessner Miracle.” The existence of this video, and even more its title, indicate that while the “what” of Moessner’s process is understood, its “how” and even more its “why” are still elusive. And indeed all the proofs of Moessner’s theorem involve more complicated concepts than both the theorem and the process.

This article identifies that Moessner’s process implements an additive function with dynamic programming. A version of this implementation without dynamic programming (1) gives rise to a simpler statement of Moessner’s theorem and (2) can be abstracted and then instantiated into related additive computations. The simpler statement also suggests a simpler and more efficient implementation to compute integral powers as well as simple additive functions to compute, e.g., Factorial numbers. It also reveals the source of – to quote John Conway and Richard Guy – Moessner’s magic.

Inversion by Partial Evaluation: A Reversible Interpreter Experiment

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A computational limit of combining partial evaluation and program inversion is investigated. Using a reversible Turing machine interpreter, we show that the first Futamura and inversion projections can produce not only functionally but also textually equivalent programs. The construction of the interpreter in a reversible flowchart language is shown in full. Insights are given into the practical interplay between reversible interpreters, program inverters, and partial evaluators. We conclude that both projections must be included in our program transformation tool box.

Completing the functional approach in object-oriented languages

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The last two decades in nearly all object-oriented programming languages features are introduced which are well-known from functional programming languages. But many feature are introduced fragmentary. In Java-TX we address these features and propose a completion. Java-TX (TX standing for **T**ype **e**Xtended) is a language based on Java. The predominant new features are global type inference and real function types for lambda expressions. Global type inference means that all type annotations can be omitted, and the compiler infers them without losing the static type property.

The function types are introduced in a similar fashion as in Scala but additionally integrated into the Java target-typing as proposed in a so-called strawman approach.

In this paper, we provide an integrated presentation of all Java-TX features. The focus is on the automatic inference of type parameters for classes and their methods, and the heterogeneous translation of function types, which allows preserving the argument and return types in bytecode.

Gradual Guarantee via Step-Indexed Logical Relations in Agda

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The gradual guarantee is an important litmus test for gradually typed languages, that is, languages that enable a mixture of static and dynamic typing. The gradual guarantee states that changing the precision of a type annotation does not change the behavior of the program, except perhaps to trigger an error if the type annotation is incorrect. Siek et al. (2015) proved that the Gradually Typed Lambda Calculus (GTLC) satisfies the gradual guarantee using a simulation-based proof and mechanized their proof in Isabelle. In the following decade, researchers have proved the gradual guarantee for more sophisticated calculi, using step-indexed logical relations. However, given the complexity of that style of proof, there has not yet been a mechanized proof of the gradual guarantee using step-indexed logical relations. This paper reports on a mechanized proof of the gradual guarantee for the GTLC carried out in the Agda proof assistant.

Global Type Inference for Java using Answer Set Programming

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Global type inference for Java is able to compute correct types for an input program which has no type annotations at all, but turns out to be NP-hard. Former implementations of the algorithm therefore struggled with bad runtime performance. In this paper we translate the type inference algorithm for Featherweight Generic Java to an Answer Set Program. Answer Set Programming (ASP) promises to solve complex computational search problems as long as they are finite domain. This paper shows that it is possible to implement global type inference for Featherweight Generic Java (FGJ) as an ASP program. Afterwards we compared the ASP implementation with our own implementation in Java exposing promising results. Another advantage is that the specification of the algorithm can be translated one on one to ASP code leading to less errors in the respective implementation. Unfortunately ASP can only be used for type inference for a subset of the Java type system that excludes wildcard types.

Explicit Weakening

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I present a novel formulation of substitution, where facts about substitution that previously required tens or hundreds of lines justify in a proof assistant now follow immediately—they can be justified by writing the four letters “refl”. The paper is an executable literate Agda script, and source of the paper is available as an artifact.

Not all consequences of the pandemic have been awful. For the last three years, I’ve had the great pleasure of meeting with Peter Thiemann and Jeremy Siek for a couple of hours every week, via Zoom, exploring topics including core calculi, gradual typing, and formalisation in Agda. The work reported here arose from those discussions, and is dedicated to Peter on the occasion of his 60th birthday.

Schedule

12:30	<i>Reception with sparkling wine and pretzels</i>	
13:30	<i>Welcome</i>	
14:00	<i>Gradual Guarantee via Step-Indexed Logical Relations in Agda</i>	Jeremy Siek
14:30	<i>Dowsing: Search by types, fast, correct and complete</i>	Gabriel Radanne
15:00	<i>Inversion by Partial Evaluation: A Reversible Interpreter Experiment</i>	Robert Glück
15:30	<i>Coffee break</i>	
16:00	<i>Completing the functional approach in object-oriented languages</i>	Martin Plümicke
16:30	<i>Global Type Inference for Java using Answer Set Programming</i>	Andreas Stadelmeier
17:00	<i>Teaching functional programming</i>	Michael Sperber
17:30	<i>Closing and organisation of carpooling</i>	
approx. 18:00	<i>Arrival of guests in Bad Krozingen</i>	
approx. 19:00	<i>Barbecue</i>	
tbd	<i>Carpooling of guests back to Freiburg</i>	